

2023

Issue One

iPlaces TETIAROA

Explore the science
happening on Tetiaroa

**Scientific:
Reports & Data
Trust**

**Cultural:
Biocultural
Notices**

**Legal:
Permits and Use
Agreements**

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iPlaces TETIAROA

A Journal of the Tetiaroa Society

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Tetiara Society

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Tetiara Ecostation
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Frank Murphy

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Neil Davies

Additional Credits

Photos are from the Tetiara Society website and from the Smithsonian Institute website. Text is from project applications, protocols and TS website. Mock up was designed by Erin Robinson and Neil Davies.

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LETTER

from the

SCIENCE DIRECTOR

“Our science credibility is only as good, in my opinion, as the composition and process of accepting and conducting science on the island.”

- Richard Bailey, Chairman and CEO of Pacific Beachcomber, S.C.

Welcome to the first edition of iPlaces Tetiaroa! This digital magazine mock-up is a long-time in the making. It brings together the tremendous effort of scientists, the Tetiaroa Ecostation staff and the Tetiaroa Society to highlight some of the incredible work happening on Tetiaroa. It answers the call from Dick Bailey to find a way

to document the science happening on Tetiaroa. iPlaces is a platform that integrates tools focused on the critical early ‘field’ phases of research projects that sample and digitize social-ecological systems. Researchers submit and publish their projects seen in this magazine’s article on ARMS for biodiversity baseline.

We link the projects together with additional data and publications as those are created from the downstream analysis and publications. In the figure below you can see the samples from the ARMS project on a global platform, iSamples.

We are looking forward to your feedback and evolving iPlaces Tetiaroa with your feedback. Please let us know what else you'd like to see included.

-Neil Davies
Tetiaroa Society,
Science Director

SCIENTIFIC

UPDATES

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This is an example project marker paper

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These are example scientific protocols shared for work done on Tetiaroa.

ARMS FOR BIODIVERSITY BASELINES IN POLYNESIE FRANCAISE

ARMS were deployed for the first time at two sites on Tetiaroa in the spring of 2014 and recovered in June 2015.

The collected communities will be processed to establish the first ever biodiversity profile for Tetiaroas reefs.

By Chris Meyer.
Photography by Smithsonian Institute

RESEARCH ARTICLE

#Ecology

#Environmental Science

ARMS for Biodiversity Baselines in Polynesie**Francaise**Christopher Meyer^a, David Liittschwager^b, Emily Schmeltzer^a, Jessica Goodheart^d, Ryan Lauter^b, Zachariah Kobrinsky^b

a: California State University (CSU), Moss Landing Marine Laboratories, b: National Geographic Society, c: Smithsonian Institution, d: University of Maryland

*For Correspondence: Christopher Meyer

Competing Interest:

Received: 22.04.2015

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ARMS were deployed for the first time at two sites on Tetiaroa in the spring of 2014 and will be recovered in June 2015. The collected communities will be processed to establish the first ever biodiversity profile for Tetiaroas reefs.

ARMS for Biodiversity Baselines in Polynesie FrancaiseChristopher Meyer¹, David Liittschwager², Zachariah Kobrinsky¹, Jessica Goodheart³, Emily Schmeltzer⁴, and Ryan Lauter²

1

[Smithsonian Institution](#)

2

[National Geographic Society](#)

3

[California State University \(CSU\), Moss Landing Marine Laboratories](#)

4

[University of Maryland](#)**Cite**Meyer, C., Liittschwager, D., Schmeltzer, E., Goodheart, J., Lauter, R., & Kobrinsky, Z. (2015). *ARMS for Biodiversity Baselines in Polynesie Francaise*. Tetiaroa Society. <https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.31069>**Project Abstract - Research Objectives and Expected Results**

Fish and coral species comprise less than 1% of all coral reef biodiversity yet almost all assessments of reef status are made exclusively on those groups. Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (ARMS) are standardized sampling arrays meant to mimic the complexity of the reef and capture the other 99% of diversity. Building off the success of the Moorea Biocode Project, ARMS provide a more comprehensive baseline across taxonomic and functional domains for documenting reef diversity and monitoring changing patterns through future ocean conditions.

ARMS sample biodiversity over precisely the same surface area in the exact same manner. Like pre-fabricated housing, ARMS are deployed on the ocean bottom for one year and then collected to see what species have moved in. The integration of traditional taxonomic methods with DNA barcoding and next-generation

References & Prior work

Data Trust

GEOME Project Link

[GEOME](https://geome-d.b.org/reco rd /ark :/21547/C f j 2) <https://geome-d.b.org/reco rd /ark :/21547/C f j 2>

XDrive Project Link by Redflag AI

<https://www.dro p b o x . c o m/scl /f o /sn u s3mk rp h q mp wu wvzy w9/h ? r l k ey =n i 7wq h j c5i e3k r5cf wr3l sv65& d l =0>

7 Citations

THE TETIAROEA ATOLL RESTORATION

PROJECT

By Benoit Stoll
Photography by Benoit Stoll

Updates on the Tetiaroa Atoll Restoration Project (TARP)

Restoring tropical islands provides an unrivaled conservation opportunity. Island restoration programs protect our world's rare and endangered species, and might also boost the resilience of their surrounding coral reefs to the effects of climate change.

As part of its Tetiaroa Atoll Restoration Program (TARP), Tetiaroa Society is carrying out a major conservation intervention on Tetiaroa (French Polynesia) in 2021. The program aims to restore seabird populations and to establish Tetiaroa as a sanctuary for seabirds, green sea turtles, coconut crabs, and translocated endangered endemic birds. In addition, we propose to leverage the unique capacity of the site and our partners to scientifically establish the value of atoll restoration for coral reef conservation.

The conservation science we propose will extend studies that suggest seabird colonies might increase the resilience of coral reefs through the fertilizing effect of nutrients from the bird's guano. Testing this hypothesis on Tetiaroa, and demonstrating the underlying ecological mechanisms, will complement traditional Polynesian knowledge and help raise awareness of the importance of restoring natural land-sea connections for biodiversity conservation and sustainable human development.

Starting in March 2020, the current project will engage world-class experts in cutting-edge restoration, biosecurity, and scientific research. It will provide excellent training opportunities for Tetiaroa Society's team of local rangers and naturalist guides.

Such training is crucial for implementing biosecurity protocols to establish Tetiaroa as a wildlife sanctuary, allowing initiation of translocation programs for endangered birds.

Let us know if you see a bird with a band!

RECENT PROTOCOLS

Science is happening all the time at the Tetiaroa Ecostation.
Check out the recently shared scientific protocols.

Card Count and Vial Deployment/Retrieval Protocol

01

This protocol provides instructions for performing card counts and deploying/retrieving vials in order to quantify the prevalence of yellow crazy ants, *Anoplolepis gracilipes*, in given transects around Onetahi, Tetiaroa using two kinds of ant baits--sugar water and peanut butter.

Find out more -> dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.ewov1oky2lr2/v1

Tetiaroa Vegetation Sampling

02

Measurement of seedling recruitment for four native woody species, the shade cover of four herbaceous plant species, and coconuts on the Motu Ahuroa in Tetiaroa.

Find out more -> dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.261ge314yl47/v1

MAR 17, 2023

CARD COUNT AND VIAL DEPLOYMENT/RETRIEVAL PROTOCOL
 Forked from CARD COUNT AND VIAL DEPLOYMENT/RETRIEVAL PROTOCOL

Laura Grace Sandel¹, Barragan¹, Erica Garibay¹, Ellis Kiran Bengard¹, Gelt¹, Kalani Sage Moloney¹, Juliet Capriola¹, Alcala¹, clairewiegand¹, Allea Eimers¹
 University of California, Berkeley

Juliet Capriola

ABSTRACT

Procedure to conduct "Crazy Yellow Ant Sampling on Tetiaroa"
 This protocol provides instructions for performing card counts and deploying/retrieving vials in order to quantify the prevalence of yellow crazy ants, *Anoplolepis gracilipes*, in given transects around Onetahi, Tetiaroa using two kinds of ant baits--sugar water and peanut butter. In addition, the experiment tested yellow crazy ant preference for sugar water bait versus the peanut butter bait.

GUIDELINES

- Do not trespass
- Analyze site safety before conducting a sample
- Avoid trampling flora
- If a point is inside a building, just go to the next point or as close to the point as possible
- If it starts raining, stop deploying vials and card counts

MATERIALS

- White flashcard (10cm x 10cm)
- Stopwatch
- EpiCollect5 mobile app
- Gaia mobile app
- Peanut butter vials
- Sugar water vials

SAFETY WARNINGS

⚠ Wear long pants and closed toed shoes---dense underbrush

ETHICS STATEMENT

Unfortunately ants were harmed in the process.

BEFORE START INSTRUCTIONS

- Recommend wearing long sleeves, pants, a sun hat, and closed toed shoes
- Recommend putting on sunscreen and bug spray

OPEN ACCESS

DOI: dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.ewov1oky2lr2/v1

Protocol Citation: Sandel, Laura Barragan, Garibay, Kiran Bengard, Ellis Gelt, Sage Moloney, Juliet Capriola, Kalani Alcala, clairewiegand, Allea Eimers 2023. CARD COUNT AND VIAL DEPLOYMENT/RETRIEVAL PROTOCOL. protocols.io <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.ewov1oky2lr2/v1>

License: This is an open access protocol distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited

Protocol status: Working
 We use this protocol and it's working

Created: Mar 17, 2023

Last Modified: Mar 17, 2023

PROTOCOL integer ID: 78945

Card Count Protocol

- 1 If needed, scrape the ground (at least a 10x10cm area) at the site so the card sits flat on the ground (i.e. if there are branches or leaf litter, scrape them away). If you scraped the ground, wait 30 seconds before placing the card down. If you did not scrape the ground, place the card down without waiting.
- 2 Place the card down on the ground.
- 3 For 30 seconds, count the number of yellow crazy ants that cross the card.
- 4 After 30 seconds have passed, pick up the card and remove all ants from it.
- 5 Enter the number of ants counted in the card count into the appropriate field of the EpiCollect5 form.

Vial Protocol

- 7 Preparation: Divide the atoll into a series of transects labeled A-Z. Then on each transect create points 1-X. The points should create a grid on the island.
 - 7.1 Prepare 25 sugar plastic vials by soaking a napkin in sugar water and placing at the bottom of the vial
 - 7.2 Prepare 12 peanut butter (PB) plastic vials by placing 1 TBS of peanut butter at the bottom of each vial, making sure not to get any PB on the sides of the vial.

CULTURAL: BIOCULTURAL AND TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE NOTICES

This is an example of a Biocultural
Notice given for a past project.

This section would include a list of
all notices given.

Photography by Tetiaroa Society

LocalContext Notice

<https://localcontextshub.org/projects/3f341ef3-31dc-41ac-ab3b-d41481626660>

The BC (Biocultural) Notice is a visible notification that there are accompanying cultural rights and responsibilities that need further attention for any future sharing and use of this material or data. The BC Notice recognizes the rights of Indigenous peoples to permission the use of information, collections, data and digital sequence information (DSI) generated from the biodiversity or genetic resources associated with traditional lands, waters, and territories. The BC Notice may indicate that BC Labels are in development and their implementation is being negotiated.

Notification BC

(Bioculturelle) French

La notification BC sert à rendre visible l'information selon laquelle le matériel utilisé est accompagné de droits culturels et de responsabilités qui nécessitent une attention particulière au moment de le partager ou de l'utiliser. La notification BC est une reconnaissance des droits des peuples autochtones de permettre l'utilisation d'informations, de collections, de données et d'informations sur les séquences numériques provenant de la biodiversité et des ressources associées à leurs terres, cours d'eau et territoires traditionnels. La notification BC peut indiquer que les étiquettes BC (bioculturelles) sont en cours de réalisation et que leur application est en train d'être négociée. Pour plus d'information à propos des étiquettes BC, consulter le site <https://localcontexts.org/notices/biocultural-notices/>.

LEGAL: PERMITS AND USE AGREEMENTS

Moorea Biocode Access and Benefits Sharing Agreement

The document was drawn up as part of the Moorea Biocode Project after broad consultation with academic and government partners and participation in the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Ad Hoc Open-ended Working Group on Access and Benefit-sharing. When the Moorea Biocode Project was launched, the Convention on Biological Diversity's (CBD) ABS protocol was not yet formalized and the Bonn Guidelines served as a framework for those wishing to conform to the "spirit of the CBD". Despite the absence of a legal framework for ABS, Moorea Biocode Project developed with French Polynesia this document as a model (or template) for similar studies and to assist French Polynesia and other authorities in considering their future policy options.

Davies, N., & Hirsch, L. P. (2010). Moorea Biocode Access and Benefit Sharing Agreement. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7150710>

ACCESS & BENEFIT SHARING AGREEMENT

BETWEEN FRENCH POLYNESIA AND THE REGENTS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA AT BERKELEY

THIS AGREEMENT [insert reference identifier] is between French Polynesia (“French Polynesia”) and the Regents of the University of California on behalf of the Berkeley campus (“UCB”)

In view of the organic law n°2004-192 of the 27th of February 2004, concerning the self government status of French Polynesia and the law n°2004-193 of the 27th of February 2004 completing the self government status of French Polynesia;

In view of the decree n°1355/PR of the 19th of April 2008 03017/PR modified, appointing the Vice president and the others ministers of the Government of French Polynesia and defining their responsibilities;

In view of the general agreement n°7.0879 of the 24th of October 2007 for cooperation between

French

Polynesia and the Regents of the University of California;

In view of the agreement which was fully executed on 2 March 2009 between the Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes (EPHE) and the Regents of the University of California on behalf of the Berkeley campus to form a scientific research partnership between the Centre de Recherches Insulaires et Observatoire de l’Environnement (CRIOBE) and the Richard B. Gump South Pacific Research Station in Moorea (hereinafter the “Moorea Ecostation”);

In view of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) concluded at Rio de Janeiro on 5 June 1992; In view of the Bonn Guidelines adopted at the World Summit on Sustainable Development held in Johannesburg in 2002;

WITNESSETH:

- 1) WHEREAS within the context of the CBD, French Polynesia has the legal authority to grant prior informed consent and authorization to access and use the biodiversity of French Polynesia;
- 2) WHEREAS the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation granted UCB financial support (hereinafter the “Grant”) for the Moorea Biocode Project (“Project”), a scientific research program with the following objectives:
 - (i) to make the exhaustive inventory of Moorea’s biodiversity, including all species of fauna and flora – plants, animals, algae, fungi, and some microbial groups;
 - (ii) to test new technological and scientific approaches for the analysis of biodiversity patterns and ecological processes in general; and

22/23 PROJECTS

This is a curated list of projects to give a sense of the breadth of work being done on Tetiaroa

Island Sustainability Program

Stewart, H., Roderick, G., & Group. (2023). ISP 2023. Tetiaroa Society.
<https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.50194>

Biotic Interactions and the Structure and Function of Coral Reefs

Hay, M., & Montoya, J. (J. (2022). BIOTIC INTERACTIONS AND THE STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION OF CORAL REEFS. Tetiaroa Society.
<https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.50137>

CIRAP Archaeological Project

Molle, G., Rurua, V., Hermann, A., Dotte-Sarout, E., Scorsini, E., & Traversat, G. (2022). CIRAP Archaeological project. Tetiaroa Society.
<https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.49960>

Effects of rat eradication on groundwater quality of freshwater lenses

Hagedorn, K., & Justis, E. (2022). Effects of rat eradication on groundwater quality of freshwater lenses. Tetiaroa Society.
<https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.48868>

Mosquito Feeding Preference Tetiaroa

BOSSIN, H., MATHIEU-DAUDE, F., Vergnaud, C., McAuley, A., Blasdell, K., Trewin, B., & ROBSON, J. (2022). Mosquito Feeding Preference Tetiaroa. Tetiaroa Society.
<https://doi.org/10.17913/F3/100501.48843>

All Prior Projects

Find out more about all the science happening on Tetiaroa at iPlaces Prior Work page: <https://place-based-research.cloud68.co/pbr/past-projects/>

SUBMIT

Submit projects and reports to iPlaces

IPLACES TETIAROA

Learn more about all the science that has happened on Tetiaroa, read scientific papers and explore the data

SUSTAINABILITY AND
CONSERVATION ARE THE REASON
FOR BEING

Support science here by making a
charitable contribution to the
Tetiara Society 501(c) 3

TETIAROA SOCIETY

2023
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